

EFFECT ON FINGERING PHENOMENON IN FRACTURED POROUS MEDIUM WITH SPECIFIC VALUE OF VARIATION IN SATURATION AT INTERFACE

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Abstract: During the water flooding process, water is injected into the petroleum reservoir, which results in the displacement of oil. This displacement occurs in a way that creates unstable water-filled fingers, leading to an important phenomenon known as instability or fingering. An approximate analytical solution has been derived for the governing non-linear partial differential equation related to instability phenomena. This solution is expressed as an ascending power series, effectively representing the saturation of injected water in this context. It provides a distribution of phase saturation for the injected water based on suitable boundary conditions. Proper initial and boundary conditions have been applied in this analysis

Keywords: Fingering Phenomenon, Capillary pressure, Fractured Porous Media, Similarity transformation.

1. INTRODUCTION

An oil reservoir consists of a porous material, with its pores filled with various hydrocarbon substances, commonly referred to simply as "oil." The heterogeneous nature of the porous medium indicates that properties of the rock, such as porosity and permeability, can differ significantly across various locations. The oil fields known as "fractured oil fields" are the most diverse, comprising clusters of porous medium blocks that are divided by a network of fractures. The process of recovering oil consists of three stages: (i) the primary recovery process, (ii) the secondary oil recovery process, and (iii) the enhanced oil recovery process. During the primary recovery phase, oil is extracted from the oil reservoir without external influence; however, in the secondary oil recovery phase, the residual oil within the porous media can be retrieved by the injection of various fluids, such as water, gas, steam, and polymers. Instability (fingering) occurs due to the injecting force, difference of viscosity and wettability of the water and oil gives rise to the protuberances (instability) at common interface. The injected water will shoot through the porous medium at relatively high speed through the inter connected capillaries and its shape is as good as fingers, therefore it is also called fingering phenomenon and fingers are unstable due to the injecting force, so it is also known as instability phenomenon. Various researchers have examined this phenomenon from multiple perspectives. Borana et al. [4] The analysis of fingers has incorporated the capillary pressure. Scheidegger [11] has provided an overview of the instabilities associated with displacement fronts in porous materials and highlighted the most relevant technique for oil extraction in the field of reservoir engineering. Therefore, during the oil recovery process, it is important to keep the fingers steady. Verma [2] examined the statistical behavior of fingering that occurs during a displacement process within a heterogeneous porous medium influenced by capillary pressure. [7] Patel Kaushal et al demonstrate the analytical method to analysis saturation of water decrease with an increase in injected fluid and time. Patel et al [8] [9]. An approximate solution of fingering phenomenon in heterogeneous porous medium with mean pressure explained and fingering phenomena in fluid flow through fracture porous media with inclination and gravitational effect and investigate the applicability of Adomian decomposition method. Meher et al. [6] developed the analytical

solution of instability phenomenon by Exponential self-similar solution technique with the presence of capillary pressure effect

2. MATHEMATICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Certain assumptions were considered when mathematically formulating this phenomenon. The instability phenomenon in heterogeneous porous media has been investigated under essential basic assumptions: immiscible flow of two incompressible fluids, water and oil; the porous medium is isotropic, incompressible, finite in extent, with a horizontal and impermeable bottom boundary; mass is conserved, and gravitational forces are neglected. The natural oil field is substantial enough to analyse the effects of water injection (water flooding) on the oil recovery process. To examine the instability phenomenon in heterogeneous porous media, we selected a cylindrical piece of porous matrix with length L , where three sides are impermeable except for one end, from which water is injected. The stability of the water flood relies on the mobility ratio between oil and water, the heterogeneity of the porous medium, fluid segregation in the reservoir, and the dissipation of fluid fronts due to capillary pressure. These frontal instabilities are typically characterized by numerous penetrating fingers of the displacing fluid. Consequently, all oil at the initial boundary $x = 0$ (where x is measured in the direction of displacement) is displaced a distance L due to water injection.

Figure 1: Representation of Fingering Phenomenon in a cylindrical piece of heterogeneous porous matrix.

3. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

During the injection process, The seepage velocities of injected water V_w and native oil V_o are expressed by Darcy's law as, [3]

$$V_w = -\frac{k_w}{r_w} K \frac{\partial P_w}{\partial x} \tag{3.1}$$

$$V_o = -\frac{k_o}{r_o} K \frac{\partial P_o}{\partial x} \tag{3.2}$$

Where, K is a variable permeability of the Fractured porous medium, k_w and k_o are relative permeability of displacing fluid and native fluid. P_o and P_w are pressures; r_w and r_o are the constant kinematics viscosities of the displacing and native fluids. The equations of continuity for these two fluids are expressed as,

$$m \frac{\partial S_w}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial V_w}{\partial x} = 0 \tag{3.3}$$

$$m \frac{\partial S_o}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial V_o}{\partial x} = 0 \tag{3.4}$$

Where, $m = m(x)$ is the porosity of the fractured porous media. From the definition of phase saturation [11] [9],

$$S_w + S_o = 1 \tag{3.5}$$

$$P_c(S_w) = P_o - P_w \tag{3.6}$$

We consider the capillary pressure and relative permeability function for water as [5],

$$P_c = \beta(S_w^{\frac{1}{2}} - C_0) \tag{3.7}$$

Where, β and C_0 are constant of proportionality. The standard relationship between the relative permeability and phase saturation was [5],

$$K_w = S_w^3 \tag{3.8}$$

$$K_o = 1 - \alpha S_w$$

Where, α is constant and its value is $\alpha = 1.11$ Since, The porosity and permeability of fractured porous media [1],

$$m(x) = \frac{1}{a - bx} \tag{3.9}$$

$$K(x) = K_c m(x) \tag{3.10}$$

Where, $a - bx \geq 1$; where, a and b are constants,

For saturation, the equation of motion can be obtained by substituting the Equation (3.1) and Equation (3.2) in continuity of the equations respectively, we get

$$m \frac{\partial S_w}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{k_w}{r_w} K \frac{\partial P_w}{\partial x} \right) \tag{3.11}$$

$$m \frac{\partial S_o}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{k_o}{r_o} K \frac{\partial P_o}{\partial x} \right) \tag{3.12}$$

Eliminating $\frac{\partial P_w}{\partial x}$ from Equation (3.11) and Equation (3.6), we have

$$m \frac{\partial S_w}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{k_w}{r_w} K \left(\frac{\partial P_o}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial x} \right) \right] \tag{3.13}$$

Now From, Equation (3.12) and using Equation (3.13) we derive,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\left(\frac{k_w}{r_w} K + \frac{k_o}{r_o} K \right) \frac{\partial P_o}{\partial x} - \frac{k_w}{r_w} K \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial x} \right] = 0 \tag{3.14}$$

Integrating Equation (3.14) we get,

$$\left[\left(\frac{k_w}{r_w} K + \frac{k_o}{r_o} K \right) \frac{\partial P_o}{\partial x} - \frac{k_w}{r_w} K \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial x} \right] = -V \tag{3.15}$$

Where, V is the constant of Integration. From Equation (3.15),

$$\frac{\partial P_o}{\partial x} = \frac{V}{\left[\frac{k_w}{r_w}K + \frac{k_o}{r_o}K\right]} + \frac{\frac{k_w}{r_w}K}{\left[\frac{k_w}{r_w}K + \frac{k_o}{r_o}K\right]} \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial x} \quad (3.16)$$

By putting the values of $\frac{\partial P_o}{\partial x}$ in Equation (3.13) it gives,

$$m \left(\frac{\partial S_w}{\partial t} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\frac{k_o}{r_o}K}{\left(1 + \frac{k_o r_w}{r_o k_w}\right)} \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial x} - \frac{V}{\left(1 + \frac{k_o r_w}{r_o k_w}\right)} \right] = 0 \quad (3.17)$$

The value of the pressure of oil (P_o) can be written as

$$P_o = \bar{P} + \frac{1}{2} P_c$$

$$\frac{\partial P_o}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial x} \quad (3.18)$$

Where, \bar{P} is the mean pressure and is constant.

Substituting the value of $\frac{\partial P_o}{\partial x}$ in Equation (3.15) it gives

$$V = \frac{1}{2} K \left[\frac{k_w}{r_w} - \frac{k_o}{r_o} \right] \left(\frac{\partial P_c}{\partial x} \right) \quad (3.19)$$

Substituting the Equation (3.19) into Equation (3.17), We obtain,

$$m \left(\frac{\partial S_w}{\partial t} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{k_w}{r_w} K \frac{dP_c}{dx} \frac{\partial S_w}{\partial x} \right] = 0 \quad (3.20)$$

Substituting Equations (3.7,3.8) and Equation (3.10) into Equation (3.20), We get

$$m \left(\frac{\partial S_w}{\partial t} \right) - \frac{1}{4} \frac{\beta K_c}{r_w} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[m S_w^{\frac{3}{2}} \frac{\partial S_w}{\partial x} \right] = 0 \quad (3.21)$$

This is non-linear partial differential equation expressing the instability phenomena in heterogeneous porous matrix during secondary recovery process which gives saturation of injected water for any distance x for $t \geq 0$.

4. SOLUTION OF THE PROBLEM

Dimensionless Variable are chosen as follow,

$$X = \frac{x}{L}, \quad T = \frac{1}{4} \frac{\beta K_c}{r_w L^2} t \tag{4.1}$$

Substituting this Value in Equation (3.21), we have,

$$\frac{\partial S_w}{\partial T} - \left(\frac{\partial S_w^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\partial X} \right) \left(\frac{\partial S_w}{\partial X} \right) - \frac{1}{m} \frac{\partial m}{\partial X} S_w^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{\partial S_w}{\partial X} \right) - S_w^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 S_w}{\partial X^2} \right) = 0, \tag{4.2}$$

Equation (4.2) is non-linear partial differential equation, for the sake of simplicity of the problem here the term $\frac{1}{m} \frac{\partial m}{\partial X}$ has been simplified as [10],

$$\frac{1}{m} \frac{\partial m}{\partial X} = \frac{\partial}{\partial X} (\log m) = L \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) = \frac{L}{2\sqrt{T}} \text{ (neglating the higher term of } X \text{)}, \tag{4.3}$$

Where, $\frac{b}{a} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{T}}$ for any $0 < T \leq 1$, Hence Eq. (4.2) will be,

$$\frac{\partial S_w}{\partial T} - \left(\frac{\partial S_w^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\partial X} \right) \left(\frac{\partial S_w}{\partial X} \right) - \left(\frac{L}{2\sqrt{T}} \right) S_w^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{\partial S_w}{\partial X} \right) - S_w^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 S_w}{\partial X^2} \right) = 0 \tag{4.4}$$

The Appropriate Boundary Condition to Solve Eq. (4.4) as,

$$S_w(X, 0) = 0 = S_{wc} \text{ for any } X > 0, \tag{4.5}$$

$$S_w(0, T) = 1 = S_{wo} \text{ for any } T > 0 \tag{4.6}$$

$$S_w(1, T) = 0 = S_{wi} \text{ for any } T > 0 \tag{4.7}$$

Choose the Similarity Transformation,

$$, \quad S_w(X, T) = f(\eta), \quad \text{where, } \eta = \frac{X}{2\sqrt{T}} \tag{4.8}$$

The governing Eq. (4.4) reduce to an ordinary differential equation together with boundary condition (4.5) and (4.6) we have,

$$f(\eta)^{\frac{3}{2}} f''(\eta) + \frac{3}{2} f(\eta)^{\frac{1}{2}} f'^2(\eta) + L f(\eta)^{\frac{3}{2}} f'(\eta) + \eta f'(\eta) = 0, \quad , \tag{4.9}$$

With the Boundary Conditions Eq. (4.5) and Eq. (4.6),

$$f(0) = S_{w_0}, X = 0, T > 0 \tag{4.10}$$

$$f(\infty) = S_{w_c}, X > 0, T = 0 \tag{4.11}$$

$$f'(0) = \omega \neq 0, T > 0 \tag{4.12}$$

To find successive coefficients of Maclaurin's series at $\eta = 0$. By taking n th derivative of Eq. (4.9), solving for $f^{(n+2)}(\eta)$ and evaluating at $\eta = 0$, we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(\frac{d^k}{d\eta^k} f(\eta)^{\frac{3}{2}} \right) f^{(n-k+2)}(\eta) = -\frac{3}{2} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(\frac{d^k}{d\eta^k} f(\eta)^{\frac{3}{2}} \right) \left(\frac{d^{n-k}}{d\eta^{n-k}} (f'(\eta))^2 \right) - L \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(\frac{d^k}{d\eta^k} f(\eta)^{\frac{3}{2}} \right) f^{(n-k+1)}(\eta) - n f^n(\eta) - \eta f^{(n+1)}(\eta) \tag{4.13}$$

To solve this, we must get the derivatives of $f^{(n)}(0)$ for all $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, $f'(0)$ can be obtained from Eq. (4.11) and formula (4.9) can be used to find the derivative $f''(0)$. By entering $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, all additional higher derivatives can also be found using formula (4.13). Consequently, the intended worth of $f(\eta)$ can be computed by Maclaurin's series,

$$f(\eta) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} F^k(0) \frac{\eta^k}{k!}, \tag{4.14}$$

Therefore, We have,

$$f(\eta) = f(0) + \eta f'(0) + \frac{\eta^2}{2!} f''(0) + \frac{\eta^3}{3!} f'''(0) + \frac{\eta^4}{4!} f^{iv}(0) + \frac{\eta^5}{5!} f^v(0) + \dots \tag{4.15}$$

Now From Eq. (4.7),

$$S_w(X, T) = f(0) + \frac{X}{2\sqrt{T}} f'(0) + \frac{X^2}{8(\sqrt{T})^2} f''(0) + \frac{X^3}{48(\sqrt{T})^3} f'''(0) + \frac{X^4}{384(\sqrt{T})^4} f^{iv}(0) + \frac{X^5}{3840(\sqrt{T})^5} f^v(0) + \dots \tag{4.16}$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned} f(0) &= S_{w_0} \\ f'(0) &= \omega \\ f''(0) &= -3 \left[\frac{\omega^2}{S_{w_0}^2} + L\omega \right] \\ f'''(0) &= - \left[\frac{3 \omega^3}{4 S_{w_0}^2} + \frac{9 \omega f''}{2 S_{w_0}} + \frac{3L \omega^2}{2 S_{w_0}} + \frac{\omega}{S_{w_0}^{\frac{3}{2}}} + Lf'' \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^{iv}(0) &= - \left[\frac{6\omega f'''}{S_{wo}} - \frac{3\omega^4}{8S_{wo}^3} + \frac{9\omega^2 f''}{2S_{wo}^2} + \frac{9f''^2}{2S_{wo}} + \frac{9L\omega f''}{2S_{wo}} + \frac{3L\omega^3}{4S_{wo}^2} + \frac{2f''}{S_{wo}^{\frac{3}{2}}} + Lf'''' \right] \\
 f^v(0) &= - \left[\frac{15\omega f^4}{2S_{wo}} + \frac{6L\omega f'''}{S_{wo}} + 15\frac{f''f'''}{S_{wo}} + \frac{9L f''^2}{2S_{wo}} + \frac{15\omega^2 f'''}{2S_{wo}^2} + \left(\frac{9L}{2} + 9\right) \frac{\omega^2 f''}{S_{wo}^2} + \frac{9\omega f''^2}{4S_{wo}^2} - \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \frac{15\omega^3 f''}{4S_{wo}^3} - \frac{3L\omega^4}{8S_{wo}^3} + \frac{9\omega^5}{16S_{wo}^4} + \frac{3f'''}{S_{wo}^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right] \tag{4.17}
 \end{aligned}$$

When water is injected at a common interface during the secondary oil recovery process, Eq. (4.15) depicts the saturation of the injected fluid during the instability phenomenon in fractured porous media.

5. STUDY OF CONVERGENCE

The convergence of Maclaurin’s series is sufficient to examine the convergence of Eq. (4.16), since Eq. (4.15) reflects Maclaurin’s series in the form of η and Eq. (4.16) represents the initial values of X and T. From Eq. (4.15),

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{k+1} &= f^{k+1}(0) \frac{\eta^{k+1}}{k+1!}, \quad , \\
 u_k &= f^k(0) \frac{\eta^k}{k!} \tag{5.1}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, from using Ratio test for convergence,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|u_{k+1}|}{|u_k|} = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|f^{k+1}(0)|}{|f^k(0)|} \frac{|\eta|}{|k+1|} = 0 < 1 \tag{5.2}$$

Since, $f^{k+1}(0)$ and $f^k(0)$ are constant which is not zero and $\eta = \frac{x}{2\sqrt{T}}$ for T = 0. Hence the Eq. (4.15) absolutely convergent series then it is convergent series.

6. NUMERICAL RESULT AND DISCUSSION

When water is injected during the secondary oil recovery process, which is an ascending power series of X with time T > 0, the solution (4.16) represents the saturation of the injected fluid. The answer (4.15) which is also in terms of power series in η , satisfies constraints (4.10) and (4.11) as well. As we have just examined the first five terms in the power series, it provides a rough explanation for the instability phenomenon and also shows that the convergent power series. We saw water saturation from the graph at X = 0 when the instability phenomena happen at the common interface for a certain value of the parameter. Figure 2 depicts the graph of $S_w(X, T)$ vs distance measured from the common interface in dimensionless variables. At time T = 0.1, the saturation graph

continuously increases until $X = 1$, where it abruptly increases due to the initial unsaturation of the fractured porous medium.

For various values of X , the saturation of water increases consistently while time T grows to $T = 0.1-1$;

Figure 2: Saturation of injected fluid at different distance when $T = 0.1$ to 1 and $\omega = 0.01$, $S_{wo} = 0.0162$, $L = 5$ fixed

Table 1: Numerical value for the Fingering Phenomenon through Fractured Porous Media

X	$S_w(X,T)$									
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1
0.1	0.0162	0.0162	0.0163	0.0163	0.0163	0.0163	0.0163	0.0163	0.0163	0.0164
0.2	0.0162	0.0162	0.0163	0.0163	0.0163	0.0164	0.0164	0.0165	0.0166	0.0167
0.3	0.0162	0.0163	0.0164	0.0165	0.0166	0.0169	0.0172	0.0176	0.0182	0.0190
0.4	0.0162	0.0164	0.0167	0.0171	0.0176	0.0185	0.0197	0.0214	0.0240	0.0276
0.5	0.0163	0.0167	0.0174	0.0185	0.0201	0.0224	0.0260	0.0313	0.0391	0.0504
0.6	0.0164	0.0172	0.0188	0.0212	0.0249	0.0305	0.0390	0.0519	0.0711	0.0991
0.7	0.0166	0.0183	0.0213	0.0261	0.0335	0.0450	0.0628	0.0901	0.1311	0.1913
0.8	0.0170	0.0199	0.0253	0.0339	0.0474	0.0688	0.1025	0.1547	0.2337	0.3501
0.9	0.0175	0.0224	0.0312	0.0456	0.0687	0.1058	0.1650	0.2573	0.3979	0.6059
1	0.0183	0.0259	0.0397	0.0626	0.0998	0.1605	0.2582	0.4121	0.6475	0.9972

The Numerical Solution for the governing equation (4.4) representing instability phenomenon in fractured porous media is obtained by using Maclaurin's series given by the equation (4.15) and (4.16). The term $\frac{L}{2\sqrt{T}}$ appears in the equation (4.4) is referred as heterogeneity coefficient for the governing equation, if $\frac{L}{2\sqrt{T}} = 0$ it describes instability phenomenon in the homogeneous porous medium. The Numerical Value for the saturation of water for various values of time are shown in Table 1 Together with its graphical representation From Figure 2 It is clearly observed that the saturation of water increases with time and as increase with distance X. Hence, the physical fact of the problem is preserved in the case of fractured porous medium and noticeable amount of oil can be displaced.

7. Conclusion

In Fingering phenomenon, the power series represents the saturation of injected fluid increasing smoothly with the increase in distance X and its starts from the initial value $S_w(X, T) = 0.0162$ and variation in saturation at common interface is very small ω . The saturation rate for fingering phenomena in fractured porous media is studied and concludes that different parameter choices, as shown in Table 1 reveal a significant increase in the water saturation rate in fractured porous media See Figure 2 which show that different choice of parameter's make more significant outcome on Saturation increasing in the domain and is more suitable for physically consistence.

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